

Donation Texts from Ur during the Isin-Larsa Period

By Michèle Maggio, Université du 3e Age

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At Ur, a range of documents called “donation texts” were unearthed. They are small tablets that registered quantities of semi-precious stones, silver and gold given to the temple of Ningal, the goddess protector of the city of Ur. The items were delivered by individual, including women. These documents belong to the archives of the unique religious complex of the city which included in its centre a ziggurat. The texts were excavated by Sir L. Woolley at Ur and are now preserved in the British Museum. I started to work on these texts during my doctoral dissertation and edited them in my book on the ornamentation of the gods in the Old Babylonian period (Maggio 2012). I take great interest in these documents because they are a rich source of information on worshipping practices, despite the difficulties that persist in the interpretation of certain cuneiform signs. These difficulties make us feel as though they are written at a turning point in Mesopotamian history. In this southern city, customs were changing. There was a tension between Sumerian traditions and the Akkadian traditions being introduced in the region. This tension implies some difficulties in the use of those two languages in the documentation. It is well established in this documentation that the objects belonging to the goddess Ningal and occasionally also to other deities were undoubtedly linked to her cult at Ur. Most probably, there were chapels dedicated to these deities in the temple of Ningal. The ornamental stone fragments were probably part of a larger piece of jewellery, such as necklace, but were torn off and dedicated to Ningal by their owners. From that moment on, they became the property of the temple and were used to adorn the goddess Ningal, and maybe other statues of lesser deities. In addition, one may wonder whether a particular area of the temple of Ningal itself was used for the storage of the goods, although the available documentation does not mention it. Instead we know that the objects dedicated to the deities of the Ningal temple could be stored along with other materials in the nearby Ganunmah.

Date Range: 1970 BCE - 1850 BCE

Region: Ur (Tell al-Muqayyar)

Region tags: Middle East, Iraq

The city of Ur (modern Tell al-Muqayyar) in what is now southern Iraq.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: « An Introduction on the Divine Statues and the Objects Belonging to the Gods in Mesopotamia during the Old Babylonian Period (ca. 2000-1595 BC) », in MARAN, J. and STOCKHAMMER, Ph. (éds),

Materiality and Practice : Transformative Capacities of Intercultural Encounters, Oxbow Books, 2012, pp. 213-220.

- Source 2: L'ornementation des dieux à l'époque paléo-babylonienne : étude du matériel ayant appartenu aux dieux d'après des documents de la pratique, réflexions sur le don, l'ornementation des statues divines et la conservation des objets précieux, AOAT 393, Münster, 2012.
- Source 3: « A Mesopotamian Temple Inventory. The Case of the Early Old Babylonian Administrative Texts from Ur », in EVANS J. M. and Rossberger, E. (ed.) in cooperation with PAOLETTI, P., Ancient Near Eastern Temple Inventories in the Third and Second Millennia BCE: Integrating Archaeological, Textual, and Visual Sources. Proceedings of a conference held at the LMU Centre for Advanced Studies, November 14-15, 2016, Münchener Abhandlungen zum Alten Orient 4, München, 2019, p. 107-118.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Clay

- ↳ Clay object
 - Clay tablet

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No

- ↳ Temple
 - Yes

- ↳ Shrine
 - Yes
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– No

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?
– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?
– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?
– I don't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?
– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?
– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– I don't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Mainly Ningal, but also Annunītum, Bawa, Nanāja, Ningišzida, and NinurumuaDU

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: as Ningal is the wife of the god Nanna, the sumerian deity of the Moon

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

- ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - No
- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - No
- ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - Yes
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By the community?
 - Yes
 - ↳ By specific individuals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

- A city-state

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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